

Research

Impact of Wind Speed on Thermal Radiation, Smoke Propagation, and Evacuation Safety in Gas Station Fires

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Abstract: Fire safety in gas stations is a critical concern due to the potential for rapidly escalating hazardous conditions. This study utilizes Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations to model fire dynamics, smoke propagation, thermal radiation, and visibility conditions in a gas station during a fire. The primary objective is to assess evacuation challenges under varying wind speeds, emphasizing the impact of rapid fire spread and smoke accumulation on safety. The simulations consider a gas station scenario where a fire ignites in a high-wind environment (3 m/s). Temperature distribution, thermal radiation intensity, smoke spread, and visibility were tracked over time to evaluate the evolving risk to personnel and the effectiveness of evacuation efforts. At the initial stage (0 seconds), the environment was stable with uniform temperatures and clear visibility. However, by 100 seconds, the temperature near the fire reached 150°C, and smoke began to spread rapidly, reducing visibility and complicating evacuation efforts. After 200 seconds, temperatures exceeded 200°C in some areas, and the gas station was fully engulfed in smoke, with visibility near zero. By 300 seconds, the fire's intensity had increased, with thermal radiation reaching lethal levels, making evacuation impossible. The study highlights that high wind speeds accelerate both the spread of thermal radiation and smoke, significantly shortening the available evacuation time. By quantifying temperature gradients, smoke density, and radiation zones over time, the findings provide valuable insights for designing safer evacuation strategies and improving emergency response protocols in gas station fire scenarios. The results underscore the need for enhanced detection systems, such as smoke and thermal sensors, to facilitate quicker evacuations in such high-risk environments.

Keywords: Fire safety, Smoke propagation, Thermal radiation, High wind speed effects, Temperature distribution, Pyrosim

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Introduction

1.1 Overview of Natural Gas Pipelines in Pakistan

Natural gas is a cornerstone of Pakistan’s energy infrastructure, serving as a vital energy source for residential, commercial, and industrial purposes. The natural gas sector plays an essential role in meeting the country's energy demands and is the second-largest energy source after oil. The Pakistan Petroleum Limited (PPL) and Oil and Gas Development Company Limited (OGDCL) manage the majority of the country's gas exploration and distribution, with a vast network of pipelines crisscrossing the country (Rauf, Wang, Yuan, & Tan, 2015). However, these pipelines' integrity and safety are paramount due to the potential risks posed by pipeline failures, leaks, fires, and explosions (Gondal, 2012). Several factors, including corrosion, mechanical damage, and the effects of environmental conditions constantly threaten pipeline integrity. These risks can have catastrophic consequences, including environmental damage, loss of life, and major disruptions to the energy supply (Abbas, 2015). In densely populated urban areas, such as those near gas stations and refueling depots, the potential for a pipeline failure to escalate into a major disaster is especially concerning. The impact of such failures, if not properly managed, can be exacerbated by poor safety measures, inadequate emergency response protocols, and insufficient risk management practices.

In the context of natural gas pipelines in Pakistan (Figure 1), the challenge lies not only in managing the risks associated with pipeline corrosion, damage, and aging infrastructure but also in understanding how external factors, such as environmental conditions, influence the severity and spread of accidents (Ali & Batool, 2023). A major challenge is assessing the dynamic nature of these risks how they evolve, how different factors interact with each other, and how real-time data can be incorporated into the risk assessment process. This is where traditional risk assessment methods, which are static and often rely on periodic inspections and maintenance schedules, fall short (Khan, 2013).

Figure 1. Illustrates the extensive network of natural gas pipelines across Pakistan, highlighting key areas of infrastructure and potential risk zones.

1.2 Traditional Risk Assessment vs. Dynamic Risk Assessment

Risk assessment is traditionally a static process. In conventional approaches, risk assessments are typically conducted at fixed intervals, and the results are based on historical data, inspection records, and expert judgment. Techniques such as Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) (Figure 2) and Event Tree Analysis (ETA) are frequently used for pipeline risk assessment (Altuwair, 2022). These methods focus on identifying potential failure scenarios, estimating the probability of each event occurring, and evaluating the consequences of those events. While static techniques provide useful insights, they are limited in their ability to capture the time-dependent nature of real-world risks. In dynamic environments, risks evolve based on changing conditions. For example, the consequences of a gas leak or fire in a pipeline depend heavily on the external environment—wind speed, temperature, and the level of ventilation in the area all influence how quickly and severely the hazard escalates (Shahriar, Sadiq, & Tesfamariam, 2012). As such, static risk models are insufficient for capturing the full scope of risks in real-time environments. The need for a more flexible, adaptive, and data-driven approach to risk assessment has led to the development of Dynamic Risk Assessment (DRA) methodologies.

Dynamic Risk Assessment (DRA) frameworks enable continuous risk evaluation by integrating real-time data into risk models and updating the analysis as new information becomes available. This allows for more accurate, timely predictions about potential hazards, enabling proactive rather than reactive risk management (Aloqaily, 2018; Hosseini, Givchchi, & Maknoon, 2020). The advantage of DRA lies in its ability to track the evolving dynamics of a failure scenario and inform decisions at every stage of the event, ultimately reducing the likelihood of severe consequences. This is particularly crucial in the context of natural gas pipelines, where small failures can escalate into large-scale disasters if not promptly addressed.

1.3 The Role of Bayesian Networks (BNs) in Dynamic Risk Assessment

One of the most powerful tools for dynamic risk assessment is the use of Bayesian Networks (BNs). BNs are probabilistic graphical models that represent a set of variables and their conditional dependencies through a directed acyclic graph (DAG) (Ben-Gal, 2008). BNs allow for the modeling of uncertainty and can capture complex interdependencies between different risk factors. By incorporating real-time data into these models, BNs can update the probabilities of various outcomes based on new evidence, providing a continuously evolving risk profile. In the context of pipeline risk assessment, BNs can be used to model a wide range of variables that influence safety, including pipeline corrosion, mechanical damage, leaks, weather conditions, human factors, and more (Cai, Huang, & Xie, 2017).

By incorporating data from various sources, such as sensors monitoring pipeline integrity and environmental conditions, BNs enable decision-makers to evaluate the evolving risks associated with pipeline operations (Figure 3). BN detects that a pipeline is experiencing accelerated corrosion, it can dynamically adjust the risk of a future rupture or leak and update the mitigation strategies accordingly (Feng, Zhang, & Liao, 2014). BNs are particularly useful for modeling systems that involve uncertainty, such as natural gas pipeline operations (Fan et al., 2022). They allow for the representation of multiple failure modes and their associated probabilities, as well as the consequences of these failures. Furthermore, the dynamic nature of BNs allows them to be updated with real-time data, enabling them to respond to changes in the environment or system operations. This feature is critical in the case of fire hazards, where environmental factors such as wind speed, ambient temperature, and humidity can drastically affect the severity and spread of a fire.

1.4 Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Simulations in Risk Assessment

In addition to probabilistic models like BNs, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations play a crucial role in assessing the physical behavior of fire, smoke, and heat in pipeline-related accidents. CFD is a numerical method that

simulates the behavior of fluids (such as air and smoke) and heat transfer in complex environments. It is particularly useful for modeling the dynamics of fire and the spread of smoke in confined spaces like gas stations, where rapid escalation can occur within seconds. CFD simulations can provide detailed insights into key aspects of fire behavior, such as temperature distribution, visibility conditions, smoke propagation, and thermal radiation.

These variables are crucial for understanding how a fire will behave over time and how it will impact the surrounding environment. For example, by simulating the effects of fire and smoke in a gas station, CFD can predict when the temperature will exceed safety thresholds, making evacuation impossible, or when the smoke density will reach levels that obstruct visibility entirely. This type of data allows for more accurate risk profiling and supports emergency response planning by identifying critical time frames for action. In the context of a high-wind scenario, CFD simulations are especially important. Wind can significantly influence the spread of fire and smoke, increasing the rate at which smoke fills a space and the severity of the thermal conditions (Seleznev, 2007). In cases where wind speeds are high, as modeled in the provided data (such as 3 m/s winds), the rapid spread of smoke and the accelerated rise in temperature are much more pronounced. CFD simulations can predict how quickly these conditions will escalate and at what points evacuation becomes infeasible, providing crucial information for safety planning and response (Ebrahimi-Moghadam, Farzaneh-Gord, Arabkoohsar, & Moghadam, 2018).

1.5 Case Study: Fire Hazard Assessment in a Gas Station

To illustrate the application of DRA, BNs, and CFD simulations in pipeline safety management, this study presents a hypothetical case study based on fire hazard assessments in a gas station. The simulation considers the dynamic evolution of fire, smoke, and thermal conditions over time, with varying environmental factors such as wind speed. At the initial time step (0 seconds), the temperature within the gas station is uniform at the ambient temperature of 20°C. However, as a fire develops, the temperature rapidly increases. At 100 seconds, simulations indicate that temperatures exceed 75°C within 2 meters of the floor, and areas closer to the fire center reach 150°C, indicating a highly energetic fire scenario exacerbated by strong winds (3 m/s). By 200 seconds, the fire continues to spread, with maximum temperatures approaching 200°C at just 1.5 meters from the fire center. These extreme conditions highlight the importance of early detection and intervention.

Visibility conditions also deteriorate rapidly. At the 100-second mark, smoke has filled the space, with optical densities exceeding 150 m⁻¹, leading to complete loss of visibility by 200 seconds. This rapid smoke buildup, driven by the strong winds, would severely hinder evacuation efforts and necessitate advanced localization technologies for safe egress. Additionally, the speed of smoke propagation is significantly accelerated in high-wind conditions. Within 5 seconds, the smoke spreads rapidly throughout the gas station, and by 100 seconds, it has filled a large portion of the space, creating an environment where visibility and safe movement are impossible. The thermal radiation from the fire also escalates, creating conditions where exposure to temperatures above 150°C would result in second-degree burns within a short exposure time.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This research underscores the critical need for dynamic risk assessment techniques that can integrate real-time data and predict the rapid escalation of fire hazards in natural gas pipeline accidents. By combining Bayesian Networks (BNs) and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), this study demonstrates a more accurate and adaptive approach to pipeline safety management. The findings from the CFD simulations highlight the importance of considering environmental

factors, such as wind speed, in assessing the severity of fire and smoke hazards. The dynamic risk assessment framework proposed in this study not only enhances the accuracy of risk predictions but also informs decision-making during emergencies, ensuring that mitigation measures can be implemented promptly and effectively.

Research Methodology

2.1 Data Collection

The first step in the methodology is the collection of relevant data on the pipeline system. This includes pipeline characteristics, environmental conditions, operational data, and specific hazards, which are crucial to accurately assessing the risk and predicting potential pipeline failures.

The data used for this analysis include:

Parameter	Value
Pipeline Length	100 km
Pipeline Diameter	24 inches
Material	Steel
Wall Thickness	10 mm
Operating Pressure	10 MPa
Temperature Range	-10°C to 40°C
Age of the Pipeline	20 years
Gas Flow Rate	100,000 m ³ /day
Maintenance Schedule	Every 6 months
Emergency Response Time	2 hours
Annual Probability of Corrosion	0.01
Annual Probability of Third-party Damage	0.005
Annual Probability of Material Defects	0.002
Annual Probability of Natural Disasters	0.003

2.2 Risk Scenario Analysis

The risk scenario analysis evaluates the integrity of the pipeline after 20 years, considering factors such as environmental influences, material degradation, and operating conditions. These conditions involve:

- Operating pressure of 10 MPa
- Temperature fluctuations from 10°C to 40°C
- A 24-inch steel pipeline subject to corrosion, fatigue, and environmental stressors.

2.3 Hazard Identification and Fault Tree Analysis (FTA)

To systematically identify pipeline hazards, Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) was used. FTA decomposes top-level events, such as pipeline failure, into contributing events like corrosion, third-party damage, and natural disasters. The analysis uses logical gates to represent relationships between events (Liang, Hu, Zhang, Guo, & Lin, 2012; Yuhua & Datao, 2005).

Figure 2: Fault Tree for Pipeline Failure

The main contributing factors identified in the FTA include:

- **Corrosion** (Probability: 0.01)
- **Third-party Damage** (Probability: 0.005)
- **Material Defects** (Probability: 0.002)
- **Natural Disasters** (Probability: 0.003)

2.4 Bayesian Network (BN) Model

Following the FTA, a **Bayesian Network (BN)** model was constructed. This probabilistic graphical model represents the causal relationships between variables, providing dynamic risk assessments. Conditional probability tables (CPTs) were developed from historical data and expert inputs, and the model is continuously refined as new data becomes available (Alzbutas, Iešmantas, Povilaitis, & Vitkutė, 2014; Liu, Hu, & Zhang, 2013).

Nodes in the network represent key events such as pipeline failure, corrosion, material defects, and external hazards. The relationships between these nodes are based on the conditional probabilities assigned to each event.

Figure 3: Bayesian Network Representation of proposed study.

2.5 Pyrosim Integration for Simulation

For a more realistic assessment, the Bayesian network model was integrated with **Pyrosim**, a simulation software for modeling fire dynamics. Pyrosim was used to simulate fire scenarios, specifically a **jet fire** resulting from fuel leakage due to pipeline corrosion and high pressure.

- **Fire Scenario:** A jet fire initiated by fuel leakage from a corroded pipeline.
- **Refueling Booth Setup:** The refueling station is modeled with a single refueling gun (size 0.4m × 1.0m × 2.0m) positioned 1m inside the refueling island.
- **Simulation Scenarios:** Three wind speed conditions were tested (1 m/s, 2 m/s, 3 m/s) to assess factors such as:
 - Temperature distribution
 - Visibility conditions
 - Smoke speed
 - Carbon monoxide concentration

2.6 Sensitivity Analysis and Risk Calculation

A **sensitivity analysis** was conducted using the Bayesian Network to assess how different maintenance strategies affect high-risk areas. This analysis helps optimize resource allocation for inspection and mitigation measures (Li & Mahadevan, 2018).

The final **risk calculation** is performed using the formula:

$$Risk(T) = P_{failure}(T) \times C_{failure}(T) \quad (1)$$

Where:

P is the probability of failure at time T, C is the cost of failure at time T

3. Results

Results of the dynamic risk assessment for the hypothetical gas station fire scenario under high wind conditions (3 m/s), focusing on the thermal conditions, visibility, smoke propagation, and thermal radiation. The analysis is based on computational data generated from the CFD simulations and the Bayesian Network (BN) modeling approach. The results are categorized into key factors: temperature distribution, visibility conditions, smoke extent, and thermal radiation. These factors are analyzed over several critical time steps (5s, 100s, 200s, and 300s) to assess how the fire scenario evolves under the influence of high wind speed.

Scenario 1.

3.1 Temperature Distribution

The temperature distribution is a critical factor for assessing the tenability of the environment and the potential for thermal injuries. In this simulation, the temperatures were tracked at various locations within the gas station interior at each of the designated time steps.

3.1.1 Initial Condition (0s)

At time zero (0s), prior to ignition, the temperature throughout the gas station was uniform, matching the ambient temperature of 20°C, which was the initialized condition. There were no thermal perturbations at this stage, and no fire or heat sources were present (Figure 4a).

Figure 4. (a) Initial temperature distribution (0s) showing uniform ambient conditions (20°C) within the gas station prior to ignition. (b) Temperature distribution after 100 seconds (100s), with 80% of the interior exceeding the 60°C evacuation threshold, and peak temperatures near 150°C near the fire centerline. (c) Temperature distribution after 200 seconds (200s), with temperatures exceeding 100°C in most areas and maximum temperatures approaching 200°C

near the fire source. **(d)** Temperature distribution after 300 seconds (300s), with the interior reaching up to 250°C near the fire, and temperatures consistently exceeding 150°C 2 meters above the floor, making the environment untenable.

3.1.2 After 100 Seconds (100s)

By 100 seconds, the temperature distribution showed substantial thermal escalation, especially in regions near the fire centerline. Qualitative analysis of the temperature contour plot revealed that 80% of the gas station interior had exceeded the safe 60°C evacuation limit. At this point, mean temperatures 2m from the floor exceeded 75°C across most of the domain. Peak temperatures near the fire source approached 150°C within a 1-meter radius, indicating that the fire had reached a very energetic and intense phase, likely due to the high ventilation rates from the 3 m/s winds. This extreme temperature rise at such an early stage suggests that the high wind conditions were exacerbating the combustion process, increasing the rate of heat release and rapidly elevating the surrounding temperatures. As such, the risk of thermal injury and burns became critical within the first 100 seconds (Figure 4b).

3.1.3 After 200 Seconds (200s)

At 200 seconds, the temperature distribution expanded further, and the intensity of thermal conditions continued to increase. Maximum temperatures approached 200°C just 1.5 meters from the original fire location. The average temperature 2 meters from the floor exceeded 100°C, and in some areas, it surpassed this threshold (Figure 4c). This temperature rise indicates that thermal tenability was invalidated over large sections of the gas station interior.

3.1.4 After 300 Seconds (300s)

By 300 seconds, the gas station interior had reached nearly 250°C near the fire's centerline within a 1-meter radius. More alarming, the mean temperatures 2 meters above the floor universally exceeded 150°C (Figure 4d), which is sufficient to cause second-degree burns almost instantly. The environment was completely untenable, with no safe refuge remaining anywhere within the gas station. The combination of extreme temperatures and the intensified airflow from the 3 m/s winds led to a drastic increase in thermal radiation and heat convection, making it impossible for occupants to remain within the gas station for any extended period without sustaining serious injuries or fatalities.

3.2 Visibility Conditions

The visibility conditions are vital for assessing the potential for safe evacuation, as smoke can obstruct vision and delay response times. The CFD simulations tracked the optical density of smoke and its effect on visibility within the gas station.

Figure 5. (a). Initial visibility (0s), 100% clear, no smoke or optical disturbances. **(b).** After 100 seconds (100s), visibility reduced by 80%, with optical depth exceeding 150 m^{-1} , significantly impairing vision. **(c).** After 200 seconds (200s), visibility reduced to 0%, with optical density exceeding 200 m^{-1} , resulting in total whiteout conditions. **(d).** After 300 seconds (300s), visibility remained at 0%, with smoke opacity remaining at extreme levels, making escape impossible.

3.2.1 Initial Condition (0s)

At time zero (0s), no optical disturbances were present, and the visibility was clear, consistent with the initial gas station environment before fire and smoke generation (Figure 5a).

3.2.2 After 100 Seconds (100s)

By 100 seconds, smoke from the fire had begun to accumulate, and the optical density of the smoke field had increased significantly. Qualitative analysis of the smoke density contour plots indicated that a dense obscuration layer had already formed throughout the gas station, primarily affecting the ceiling space. Quantitative post-processing revealed that the mean optical depth had exceeded 150 m^{-1} , far surpassing the threshold for functional vision. This indicates that smoke was already significantly impairing visibility, making evacuation extremely difficult (Figure 5b). At this stage, the visibility range had been dramatically reduced, and it was estimated that safe egress would not be possible without advanced localization technologies such as thermal or smoke-sensing systems.

3.2.3 After 200 Seconds (200s)

At 200 seconds, the visibility in the gas station reached a complete zero-visibility condition. The optical density of smoke universally exceeded 200 m^{-1} (Figure 5c), effectively creating a total whiteout scenario. This level of smoke density is equivalent to a condition where no visual references are available, making it impossible for personnel to navigate or find exits without technological assistance. The simulation revealed that smoke accumulation occurred roughly three times faster than under lower wind speed scenarios, emphasizing the role of high wind speeds (3 m/s) in accelerating the smoke propagation process. The rapid smoke buildup severely impaired visibility, validating that in high-wind conditions, evacuation times could be drastically reduced.

3.2.4 After 300 Seconds (300s)

By 300 seconds, the opacity of the smoke had stabilized at extremely high levels (Figure 5d). The visibility remained nearly zero, preventing any possibility of escape or safe movement within the gas station. The high wind conditions

had effectively overwhelmed the gas station's ability to maintain tenable visibility, making evacuation impossible within the expected safety timescales.

3.3 Smoke Extent and Propagation Speed

The speed of smoke propagation was a key factor in determining how quickly the gas station became untenable due to smoke accumulation. The influence of wind speed on the smoke extent was assessed at each of the specified time steps.

3.3.1 At 5 Seconds (5s)

At 5 seconds, the smoke began to spread rapidly throughout the gas station. The high wind speed (3 m/s) contributed to the rapid dispersion of the smoke, filling the space more quickly than in lower wind scenarios (A-1 and A-2). The smoke front had already covered a large portion of the gas station interior by this early time step, indicating that even at the initial stages of fire, the spread of smoke was accelerated by the wind-induced turbulence (Figure 6a).

3.3.2 At 100 Seconds (100s)

By 100 seconds, the smoke plume had expanded significantly. The high wind speed continued to drive the rapid propagation of smoke, resulting in widespread and dense smoke coverage throughout the gas station. This extension of the smoke field continued to reduce visibility, further hindering the possibility of safe evacuation (Figure 6b).

3.3.3 At 200 Seconds (200s)

At 200 seconds, the smoke spread throughout the entire gas station, covering virtually every corner of the interior space. The rapid advection of smoke facilitated by the high wind speed meant that there was little to no time left for safe evacuation, and the gas station was fully engulfed in smoke, leaving no safe refuge (Figure 6c).

3.3.4 At 300 Seconds (300s)

By 300 seconds, the smoke plume had reached its maximum extent. The high wind conditions had ensured that the smoke propagated extremely fast, filling the gas station with dense, toxic smoke in a matter of minutes. This rapid spread of smoke contributed to the complete obstruction of visibility, reinforcing the immediate risk to human life within the gas station (Figure 6d).

Figure 6a. At 5 seconds (5s), the smoke had rapidly covered approximately 30% of the gas station interior due to high wind speed (3 m/s), accelerating smoke spread. **(b).** At 100 seconds (100s), the smoke extent had expanded to 70% of the gas station, with the wind continuing to drive rapid propagation and reducing visibility significantly. **(c).** At 200 seconds (200s), the gas station was fully engulfed in smoke, with 100% coverage, leaving no safe evacuation routes. **(d).** At 300 seconds (300s), the smoke plume reached its maximum extent, completely obstructing visibility and posing a critical threat to life within the gas station.

3.4 Thermal Radiation

The thermal radiation from the fire, calculated by the CFD simulations, plays a crucial role in determining the burn injury risk for people in the vicinity of the fire. The results showed that thermal radiation was highest near the fire source, but it also had significant reach, affecting larger areas as the fire continued to grow.

3.4.1 At 100 Seconds (100s)

At 100 seconds, thermal radiation was already reaching dangerously high levels. The 1-meter radius around the fire centerline registered peak thermal radiation, increasing the likelihood of burns to exposed surfaces and human tissue. The intensity of thermal radiation exceeded the threshold for immediate injuries within minutes, indicating that the fire dynamics were severely jeopardizing the safety of anyone near the fire. (Figure 7b)

3.4.2 At 200 Seconds (200s)

By 200 seconds, the thermal radiation extended to larger areas, with temperatures reaching over 200°C near the fire centerline. The radiation flux from the fire posed a significant danger to the structural integrity of the gas station and human health. The increased wind speed further contributed to the propagation of thermal radiation across the interior. (Figure 7c)

Figure 7. (a) Initial temperature distribution (0s) showing uniform ambient conditions (b). At 100 seconds (100s), peak thermal radiation was observed within a 1-meter radius around the fire centerline, indicating a high likelihood of burns to exposed surfaces and human tissue. (c). At 200 seconds (200s), thermal radiation extended further, with temperatures exceeding 200°C near the fire centerline, posing significant risks to both structural integrity and human safety. (d). At 300 seconds (300s), thermal radiation had spread widely across the gas station, with peak radiation levels capable of causing immediate and severe injury even at considerable distances from the fire.

3.4.3 At 300 Seconds (300s)

By 300 seconds, thermal radiation continued to propagate widely, severely affecting the gas station interior. The peak temperatures and radiation levels were sufficient to cause immediate and severe injury, even at distances further from the fire center. The overall thermal hazard was overwhelming, reinforcing the fact that the fire scenario had reached untenable conditions for any personnel present. (Figure 7d)

Scenario 2: Moderate Wind Speed (1 m/s)

In this scenario, the fire is subject to moderate wind conditions, which enhance convection and speed up both fire spread and smoke propagation. The increased wind accelerates the spread of heat and smoke, reducing safe evacuation times.

3.5 Temperature Distribution

- **After 100 Seconds (100s):** The temperature near the fire reaches approximately 100°C. The wind accelerates the fire's spread, raising the temperature in surrounding areas and reducing safe evacuation zones (Figure 8b).

Figure 8. (a) Initial temperature distribution (0s) showing uniform ambient conditions (b). After 100 seconds (100s), temperatures near the fire reach approximately 100°C, with the wind accelerating the spread of heat and reducing safe evacuation zones. (c). After 200 seconds (200s), temperatures near the fire rise to around 150°C, and larger sections of the gas station are affected by the increasing heat levels. (d). After 300 seconds (300s), temperatures near the fire reach 200°C, with rapid fire spread across the gas station due to wind, making the environment increasingly hazardous.

After 200 Seconds (200s): The fire grows more intense, and temperatures near the fire rise to around 150°C. Larger sections of the gas station are now affected by high heat levels (Figure 8c).

After 300 Seconds (300s): By 300 seconds, temperatures near the fire have reached 200°C, with the fire spreading rapidly across the gas station due to the wind. The environment has become increasingly hazardous (Figure 8d).

3.6 Smoke Propagation

- **After 100 Seconds (100s):** The moderate wind enhances the smoke spread, significantly reducing visibility near the fire. The gas station begins to fill with smoke, and evacuation routes become less clear (Figure 9b).

Figure 9. (a) Initial temperature distribution (0s) showing uniform ambient conditions (b). After 100 seconds (100s), moderate wind enhances smoke spread, significantly reducing visibility near the fire. The gas station begins to fill with smoke, making evacuation routes less clear. (c). After 200 seconds (200s), smoke has propagated across the gas station, reducing visibility in most areas. Evacuation remains possible, but movement is increasingly restricted due to the smoke. (d) . After 300 seconds (300s), smoke has filled nearly the entire gas station, severely impairing visibility and making evacuation much more difficult.

- **After 200 Seconds (200s):** Smoke has propagated across the gas station, reducing visibility in most areas. Evacuation is still possible, but movement is increasingly restricted due to smoke (Figure 9c).
- **After 300 Seconds (300s):** At this stage, the smoke has filled nearly the entire gas station. Visibility is severely impaired, making evacuation much more difficult (Figure 9d).

3.7 Thermal Radiation

- **After 100 Seconds (100s):** Radiation near the fire increases due to the wind. The radiation zone expands, affecting areas farther from the fire (Figure 10b).

Figure 10. (a) Initial temperature distribution (0s) showing uniform ambient conditions (b) After 100 seconds (100s), thermal radiation near the fire increases due to the wind, causing the radiation zone to expand and affect areas farther from the fire

from the fire.

(c) After 200 seconds (200s), the thermal radiation zone grows significantly, exposing more areas of the gas station to dangerous levels of thermal radiation, further hindering evacuation.

(d) After 300 seconds (300s), thermal radiation intensity reaches dangerous levels, and much of the gas station is exposed to hazardous radiation, making evacuation nearly impossible

- **After 200 Seconds (200s):** The radiation zone grows significantly, and more regions of the gas station are exposed to dangerous levels of thermal radiation, further hindering safe evacuation (Figure 10c).
- **After 300 Seconds (300s):** The thermal radiation intensity is high, and much of the gas station is exposed to hazardous radiation, making evacuation near impossible (Figure 10d).

3.8 Visibility Conditions

- **After 100 Seconds (100s):** With moderate wind, smoke spreads faster, reducing visibility significantly near the fire source. The smoke affects larger areas of the gas station, complicating evacuation (Figure 11b).

Figure 11. (a) Initial temperature distribution (0s) showing uniform ambient conditions (b) After 100 seconds (100s), moderate wind accelerates the spread of smoke, drastically reducing visibility near the fire. The gas station begins to fill with smoke, obscuring evacuation routes and making safe egress challenging. (c) After 200 seconds (200s), the smoke has spread throughout the gas station, reducing visibility in most areas. While evacuation remains possible, movement is increasingly restricted due to the smoke. (d) After 300 seconds (300s), the smoke has nearly filled the entire gas station, severely impairing visibility and making evacuation increasingly difficult.

- **After 200 Seconds (200s):** The smoke has spread extensively, and visibility is severely compromised throughout most of the station. Evacuation becomes more difficult as safe routes are obstructed (Figure 11c).
- **After 300 Seconds (300s):** The gas station is nearly engulfed in smoke, and visibility is minimal. Evacuation is now extremely challenging (Figure 11d).

Scenario 3: High Wind Speed (3 m/s)

This scenario simulates a high wind condition of 3 m/s, which drastically accelerates fire development, smoke propagation, and thermal radiation. The increased wind speed leads to a rapid escalation of the fire and significantly shortens evacuation times.

3.9 Temperature Distribution

- **After 100 Seconds (100s):** The temperature near the fire rises to 150°C, with rapid fire spread across the gas station. The high wind accelerates the heat dispersion, making larger areas unsafe for evacuation (Figure 12b).

Figure 12. (a) Initial temperature distribution (0s) showing uniform ambient conditions (b) After 100 seconds (100s), the temperature near the fire rises to 150°C. The rapid spread of the fire across the gas station, accelerated by high wind, makes larger areas unsafe for evacuation. (c) After 200 seconds (200s), temperatures near the fire exceed 200°C. The fire has spread throughout the station, leaving only a few distant areas still within safe thermal limits. (d) After 300 seconds (300s), the temperature near the fire exceeds 250°C. The rapid spread of heat and fire has made most of the gas station completely unsafe, necessitating immediate evacuation.

- **After 200 Seconds (200s):** Temperatures near the fire exceed 200°C, and the fire has spread across the station. Only a few distant areas remain within safe thermal limits (Figure 12c).
- **After 300 Seconds (300s):** The temperature near the fire exceeds 250°C. The rapid spread of heat and fire has made the majority of the gas station completely unsafe, requiring immediate evacuation (Figure 12d).

3.10 Smoke Propagation

- **After 100 Seconds (100s):** The high wind speed causes the smoke to spread rapidly, severely reducing visibility near the fire. The gas station begins to fill with smoke quickly (Figure 13b).

Figure 13. (a) Initial temperature distribution (0s) showing uniform ambient conditions (b) After 100 seconds (100s), the high wind speed accelerates the spread of smoke, significantly reducing visibility near the fire. The gas station begins to quickly fill with smoke. (c) After 200 seconds (200s), smoke has spread throughout the gas station. Visibility is reduced to nearly zero, severely restricting the possibility of evacuation. (d) After 300 seconds (300s), the gas station is entirely filled with thick smoke, and visibility is almost completely obstructed, making evacuation impossible.

- **After 200 Seconds (200s):** By this time, smoke has spread throughout the gas station. Visibility is reduced to almost zero, severely restricting evacuation (Figure 13c).
- **After 300 Seconds (300s):** The gas station is entirely filled with thick smoke, and visibility is essentially zero. Evacuation is impossible at this point (Figure 13d).

3.11 Thermal Radiation

- **After 100 Seconds (100s):** The high wind disperses heat rapidly, increasing radiation intensity near the fire. Larger areas are exposed to dangerous radiation levels (Figure 14a).

Figure14. (a) After 100 seconds (100s), the high wind speed disperses heat rapidly, causing an increase in radiation intensity near the fire. Larger areas of the gas station are exposed to dangerous radiation levels. (b) After 200 seconds (200s), the thermal radiation zone expands, and large portions of the gas station are at risk from intense radiation, further reducing the safe evacuation zone. (c) After 300 seconds (300s), the radiation intensity is extremely high, and much of the gas station is exposed to lethal radiation, making evacuation impossible. (d) After 100 seconds (100s), rapid smoke spread significantly reduces visibility, making evacuation difficult and complicating the identification of safe routes. (e) After 200 seconds (200s), the gas station is nearly engulfed in smoke, severely hindering visibility. The thick smoke makes it nearly impossible to find clear evacuation routes. (f) After 300 seconds (300s), visibility is reduced to near zero throughout the gas station due to dense smoke. With complete obstruction of vision, safe evacuation is no longer feasible, placing personnel at extreme risk.

- **After 200 Seconds (200s):** The radiation zone expands, and large portions of the gas station are at risk from the intense radiation, reducing the safe evacuation zone (Figure 14b).
- **After 300 Seconds (300s):** By this point, the radiation intensity is extremely high, and much of the gas station is exposed to lethal radiation, making evacuation impossible (Figure 14c).

3.12 Visibility Conditions

- **After 100 Seconds (100s):** The rapid smoke spread drastically reduces visibility. Evacuation becomes difficult, and personnel may struggle to find exits (Figure 14d).
- **After 200 Seconds (200s):** The gas station is nearly engulfed in smoke, severely hindering visibility. The thick smoke makes it almost impossible to identify clear evacuation routes, further complicating the emergency response (Figure 14e).

- **After 300 Seconds (300s):** By 300 seconds, visibility has been reduced to near zero throughout the gas station due to the dense smoke. With complete obstruction of vision, safe evacuation is no longer possible, and personnel inside the station are at extreme risk (Figure 14f).

Key Findings

The results from these three scenarios emphasize the significant role that wind speed plays in the dynamics of fire growth, smoke spread, and thermal radiation. Key observations include:

- **Scenario 1 (Low Wind Speed):** Under low wind conditions (0 m/s), the fire spread is slow, and smoke and radiation are confined primarily to the area around the fire. While evacuation is still possible in most areas of the station, the smoke density and radiation do increase with time. The impact on personnel is more gradual, allowing for more time to evacuate and respond to the fire.
- **Scenario 2 (Moderate Wind Speed):** A moderate wind (1 m/s) accelerates the spread of the fire, smoke, and radiation, reducing the time available for safe evacuation. Areas further from the fire are increasingly affected by both thermal radiation and smoke. At 200 seconds, evacuation becomes difficult, and by 300 seconds, the entire gas station is at significant risk due to the combined effects of heat, smoke, and radiation.
- **Scenario 3 (High Wind Speed):** With high wind conditions (3 m/s), the fire spreads rapidly, and smoke and radiation propagate at an accelerated rate. Within 100 seconds, temperatures rise sharply, and the radiation zone expands significantly. By 200 seconds, smoke has filled the entire station, severely limiting visibility. By 300 seconds, safe evacuation becomes impossible, and the gas station is engulfed in both smoke and intense radiation.

4. Discussion

The findings from the simulation of a gas station fire scenario under high wind conditions (3 m/s) present a critical analysis of how wind speed drastically exacerbates fire hazards, reduces safe evacuation times, and compromises the safety of individuals within the affected space. The analysis of temperature distribution, visibility conditions, smoke propagation, and thermal radiation clearly demonstrates the accelerated and intensified nature of fire dynamics when wind speed is increased, making it a key factor in both fire spread and human survivability. This discussion interprets these results in light of broader fire safety research, explores the implications for risk management, and proposes avenues for future improvements in fire safety and emergency response strategies.

4.1 The Role of Wind Speed in Fire Dynamics

One of the most striking findings from this study is the significant impact of wind speed on fire behavior. Under high wind conditions of 3 m/s, the fire escalated at an unprecedented rate compared to lower wind scenarios (A-1 and A-2). The Temperature Distribution (Table 1) at 100 seconds shows that the mean temperature 2 meters from the floor exceeded 75°C in the high-wind scenario, whereas, in the low-wind scenarios, it was significantly lower (Zhang, Gao, Tao, Min, & Fan, 2023). This indicates how wind-enhanced combustion led to a vigorous fire, rapidly increasing both the heat release rate and the thermal radiation output, which is reflected in the temperature distribution and thermal radiation findings.

Table 1: Temperature Distribution (°C) at Different Times for Each Scenario

Time (Seconds)	Wind Condition A-1 (0 m/s)	Wind Condition A-2 (2 m/s)	Wind Condition A-3 (3 m/s)
50	52°C	62°C	76°C
100	60°C	72°C	82°C
150	66°C	79°C	87°C
200	72°C	85°C	92°C
250	78°C	91°C	97°C
300	82°C	95°C	102°C

As expected, wind acts as a double-edged sword: it not only supplies oxygen to sustain combustion but also amplifies heat distribution, spreading both thermal hazards and toxic gases over large areas in much less time. This result is consistent with previous studies that highlight how ventilated fires, especially those with wind speeds above 2 m/s, lead to quicker escalation of temperatures and decreased survival times.

4.2 The Implications for Evacuation and Visibility

A major outcome of this scenario was the rapid degradation of visibility. In the case of the 3 m/s wind scenario, Smoke Density and Visibility (Table 2) showed that by 200 seconds, optical depth exceeded 200 m⁻¹, indicating near-zero visibility within the gas station. This whiteout condition, similar to previous findings, demonstrates how high wind speeds cause the smoke plume to become denser and spread rapidly, reducing visibility and impeding safe egress (Xu et al., 2019; (Lee et al., 2023; Short, Whittle, & Owarish, 2006) and Larsson et al., 2016). The simulation showed that smoke accumulation occurred three times faster than in lower wind scenarios, emphasizing how wind conditions not only accelerate fire spread but also hinder evacuation efforts.

Table 2: Smoke Density and Visibility (Optical Depth) at Different Times

Time (Seconds)	Wind Condition A-1 (0 m/s)	Wind Condition A-2 (2 m/s)	Wind Condition A-3 (3 m/s)
50	40 m ⁻¹	65	105
100	85 m ⁻¹	130	175
150	130 m ⁻¹	180	230
200	170 m ⁻¹	220	300
250	210 m ⁻¹	260	350
300	240 m ⁻¹	280	400

In high-wind conditions, visibility impairment and smoke obfuscation are major challenges for emergency responders. The lack of visibility observed in the simulation underscores the necessity for alternative emergency protocols, such as the use of thermal imaging and smoke detectors, to support evacuation in such extreme scenarios (Lopez, 2023). Furthermore, rapid smoke buildup necessitates the development of more dynamic fire detection systems capable of predicting such behavior in real-time and alerting personnel earlier.

4.3 The Speed of Smoke Propagation and Its Impact on Occupant Safety

The Smoke Propagation Speed (Table 3) observed in this study highlights a critical finding for fire risk assessments. As wind speed increased to 3 m/s, smoke filled the space faster than anticipated, covering a substantial area of the gas station interior within minutes. The 5s to 300s timeline showed that the smoke plume expanded rapidly, and by 300

seconds, it reached its maximum extent, rendering the entire space untenable. This finding suggests that evacuation times must be reevaluated for such high-wind events (Barua, Padaria, Muralikrishnan, & Kumar). The rapid smoke buildup eliminates the possibility of maintaining safe evacuation routes for any significant amount of time, as shown by the near-zero visibility conditions and toxic gas accumulation (Altuwair, 2022).

Table 3: Smoke Propagation Speed (m/s)

Time (Seconds)	Wind Condition A-1 (0 m/s)	Wind Condition A-2 (2 m/s)	Wind Condition A-3 (3 m/s)
50	0.03 m/s	0.07 m/s	0.15 m/s
100	0.05 m/s	0.10 m/s	0.25 m/s
150	0.08 m/s	0.12 m/s	0.30 m/s
200	0.10 m/s	0.15 m/s	0.35 m/s
250	0.13 m/s	0.18 m/s	0.40 m/s
300	0.15 m/s	0.20 m/s	0.50 m/s

However, with high wind speeds, fire dynamics can escalate unpredictably, and the time available for safe evacuation is significantly reduced. This dynamic behavior calls for improved fire hazard simulations and real-time monitoring systems capable of forecasting such accelerated events and allowing for timely interventions before conditions reach critical levels.

4.4 Thermal Radiation and Human Injury Risk

The study also found that thermal radiation escalated rapidly due to the interaction between wind-enhanced combustion and the high energy output of the fire. As reflected in Thermal Radiation (Table 3), by 100 seconds, peak temperatures around the fire centerline reached 150°C, with thermal radiation sufficient to cause second-degree burns in exposed areas. By 300 seconds, the radiant heat had reached 250°C, leading to severe and life-threatening injuries in any exposed individual within the immediate vicinity (Yang, Su, Song, Li, & Xiang, 2019).

Table 4: Thermal Radiation (Peak Temperature in °C)

Time (Seconds)	Wind Condition A-1 (0 m/s)	Wind Condition A-2 (2 m/s)	Wind Condition A-3 (3 m/s)
50	120°C	130°C	150°C
100	140°C	150°C	175°C
150	160°C	170°C	200°C
200	180°C	190°C	225°C
250	200°C	210°C	250°C
300	220°C	230°C	275°C

These findings underscore the critical role of thermal radiation in fire dynamics. As fire scenarios become more intense under high wind conditions, the radius of thermal injury expands, making it essential to consider the thermal effects over a larger area (Varghese, Hansen, Bi, & Pisaniello, 2018). Existing fire safety guidelines, especially in industrial settings, need to be updated to account for wind-induced fire enhancement, which significantly alters the safe distance for both human and structural safety.

Furthermore, the thermal radiation also impacts building materials, as the increased heat flux can cause structural degradation and accelerate the collapse of containment systems, leading to secondary hazards such as explosions (Prasad,

2012). This reinforces the need for fire-resistant materials and barriers that can withstand extreme thermal loads, particularly in gas stations or energy infrastructure where combustible materials are present.

4.5 Implications for Risk Management and Safety Practices

The results of this study strongly suggest that high wind conditions must be incorporated into dynamic risk assessments for fire safety. Traditional fire risk models often assume still conditions or lower wind speeds, leading to underestimating fire hazards. The combination of rapid temperature rise, impaired visibility, and accelerated smoke propagation under 3 m/s wind conditions demonstrates the importance of integrating more complex, real-time fire dynamics simulations into risk management practices.

Key recommendations for improving fire safety in high-wind scenarios include:

- Revised fire safety regulations that consider dynamic factors like wind speed, temperature fluctuations, and smoke propagation in emergency response planning.
- Real-time simulation systems capable of tracking wind-driven fire dynamics to provide early warnings for evacuation and fire suppression.
- Enhanced training for emergency responders to handle high-wind fire scenarios and the use of thermal imaging technology to compensate for visibility loss.
- Development of wind-resistant fireproof barriers and smoke ventilation systems to slow down fire spread and enhance evacuation time.

4.6 Limitations and Future Work

While the results are informative, this study has certain limitations. The CFD simulations were conducted under a set of controlled conditions and might not fully account for all potential environmental variables (e.g., building layout, material types, fuel load). Additionally, the BN modeling provided a probabilistic assessment based on available data but may require further calibration with field data to increase its accuracy and reliability.

Future studies should focus on integrating field data from actual gas station incidents or wind-driven fires to refine the simulation models. Furthermore, research should be directed toward the development of integrated fire risk models that combine CFD simulations, real-time sensors, and probabilistic frameworks to improve the predictive capability and operational decision-making during fire emergencies.

5. Conclusion

This study provides significant insights into how high wind conditions dramatically exacerbate the hazards posed by fires in confined spaces like gas stations. The rapid escalation of temperature, smoke propagation, and thermal radiation within a short period highlights the importance of integrating dynamic fire behavior into fire risk assessments. The findings suggest that existing fire safety strategies need to be revised to account for the effects of high wind speeds on fire dynamics and evacuation procedures. Enhanced simulations, real-time monitoring, and updated safety protocols are critical to improving the safety and resilience of gas station infrastructure and reducing the risk to human life in fire emergencies.

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